

STRUCTURAL, MECHANICAL AND WEAR PROPERTIES OF PLASMA NITRIDED GREY CAST IRON USED AS CAMSHAFT MATERIAL

O. Çomaklı ^{a*}, A. F. Yetim ^b A. Dayanç ^c, A. Çelik ^a

^a*Ataturk University, Faculty of Engineering, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Erzurum-TURKEY*

^b*Erzurum Technical University, Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Erzurum-TURKEY*

^c*ESTAŞ Eksantrik San ve Tic A.Ş, Sivas-TURKEY*

*Corresponding Author E-mail address: onurcomakli@atauni.edu.tr (O. Çomaklı)

Abstract

Cams of the camshaft contact directly with cam follower. When each cam rotates, it drives the follower away from the camshaft rotational axis. In the meantime, camshaft can be subject to wear. This wear causes to some problems such as, less valve opening, noisy operation of the valves etc. Eventually, changing of timing of the opening and closing of the valves give rise to poor combustion and reducing the engine's power. There are several surface treatments in order to overcome these problems and to optimize wear properties of cams. Plasma nitriding is one of these treatments. In this study, grey cast iron used as camshaft material has been nitrided in plasma environment under different process parameters including time (2 and 4h), temperature (450 and 500°C), and gas mixture ratio (%50 H₂ + %50 N₂ and %90 H₂ + %10 N₂). The structure, mechanical and wear properties of nitrided grey cast iron was analyzed with XRD, SEM, microhardness tester, 3D profilometer and pin on disk type tribo-tester.

Key words: Plasma nitriding; Grey cast iron; Camshaft; Wear resistance